

Low Latency Stockwell Transform Based Secured Distance Protection Scheme for Power Network Connected with High Renewable Penetration

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Abstract:

Power electronic converter (PEC) interfaced renewable energy generators (REGs) are increasingly being integrated to the power grid. With the high renewable power penetration levels, one of the key power system parameters, namely reactive power is affected, provoking steady-state voltage and dynamic/ transient stability issues. The performance of existing fault detection and phase selection scheme degrades in presence of PEC interfaced REGs power transmission network. This paper deals with a comprehensive analysis to test the performance of available distance protection, that can be used in transmission networks with high renewable power penetration levels. The performance of the different vendor distance relay is compared for different type fault in transmission line. Further, the new fast S-transform (FST) based hybrid scheme has been discussed that is capable of operating under challenging conditions. The computational complexity of FST is much lower than the S-transform. Therefore, the method is a good choice for real-time applications for the time-frequency analysis of faults in a presence of PEC interfaced REGs power transmission network. The proposed FST-based method is highly efficient and also meet the speed criteria of the relaying function when performing the task. The work is part of the EU project MIGRATE dealing with Massive Integration of Power Electronic Equipment.

Keywords: Distance protection, Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG), Power electronic converter (PEC), renewable energy generators (REGs) , Fast S-transform (FST), MIGRATE.

1. Introduction

Due to the global drive towards renewable and sustainable energy systems, power electronic converter (PEC) interfaced renewable energy generators (REGs), such as wind generators and solar-PV systems have widely been adopted in power networks around the world. The Kyoto Protocol was one of the major catalyst for the global drive towards renewable energy generation [1]. In addition, due to the technical advances in the PECs and the electronic materials, manufacturing cost of REGs have significantly reduced during the past decade while encouraging wide-scale adoption of PEC interfaced REGs in power networks [2]. In 2016, REGs were accounted for the two thirds of the new generation added to power networks, and approximately 165 GW of renewable power generation capacity was added to power networks around the world. Among renewable sources, the solar-PV capacity was grew by 50%, while exceeding the total installed capacity beyond 74 GW, which is higher than the net annual growth in coal power generation [3]. Majority of the developed countries have set renewable energy targets in power generation, and also making policy directives to achieve these targets. At the early stage of renewable energy integration, REGs could be either connected or disconnected from the power grid without significant impact on grid stability, since their penetration levels were low. However, at present with the increased renewable power generation, it is no longer possible to connect or disconnect REGs at operator's discretion, since it would adversely affect the power system protection, stability and reliability.

Furthermore, the interconnection of bulk PEC interfaced REGs should be in line with the grid codes for fault ride through capability defined by European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSOE) [4] and grid codes applied in different European countries [5] as well as their respective counterparts around the world as Federal Energy Regulatory Commission (FERC) in North America. In case of testing protection coordination, it is demanding to take into account these requirements as well as to check if the protection is still robust under different fault conditions. In order to do this, firstly a suitable test system should be built that will be capable of simulating real time conditions of different PEC interfaced REGs connected to the system[6]. The essentials of testing protection performances for converter based power system with PEC interfaced REGs was addressed

in [6-9]. It has been shown that there are many cases of nuisance tripping of the protection when Type-3 and Type-4 wind generators are used. In [10], an intelligent algorithm for the protection of smart power systems has been presented. This algorithm is developed for distribution systems and does not take into account the requirements imposed by the grid code for interconnecting renewable generation. In [11-12], the performance of the distance protection were evaluated for different faults on a line supplied by PEC interfaced REGs on one side and conventional generation on the other. In this simplified example, several cases are presented in which protection failed to eliminate different faults. The authors also proposed solutions for different cases. The used network was referred only to type 4 generators. Present protection practices have been developed for a system where synchronous generators(SG) are dominant. The behavior of this system is well known and reported by many research paper.

Therefore, this paper deals with testing the efficiency of available distance protection from different vendors, by observing system performance in hardware-in-loop(HIL) testing associated with real-time-digital-simulator(RTDS). The main objective of this paper is ;

- *HIL testing of available vendors distance protection function in presence of PEC interfaced REGs power transmission network with high renewable power penetration levels.*
- *Developing FST hybrid protection scheme to overcome the shortfall of available distance protection fault detection element limitation during phase-to-phase fault with low generation level.*

2. System studied : PEC interfaced REGs benchmark model for HIL-testing

A benchmark model that is used to study different scenarios consists of a point-to-point terminal HVDC links that are connected to wind park, solar cells and conventional generation from different sides as well as it is connected to an infinite grid. The scheme implementable in RTDS version 5.003, environment is shown in Fig.1 and it is also chosen in a way that can be easily restructured by removing one HVDC line and adding it to another branch so that various types of faults at different locations can be applied[13].

Fig. 1: System studied

The crucial components that require particular attention and modelling efforts are:

- Model of a Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG).
- Model of a full converter Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG).
- Two level VSC converter for the HVDC lines.
- Solar panel model connected to the system through a full converter.

The PV model includes the Solar Panel model, the DC bus, the power inverter and a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm [14-16]. The model contains a DC/DC and a DC/AC converter. On the other hand, the model of DFIG system include chopper and crowbar protection

elements and the PMSG [17-20] is also developed in detail in per unit value so that the output power is scaled to the corresponding penetrating power level. In order to take into account the asymmetrical fault currents, negative sequence control has also been implemented for all DGs according to [21-22]. In this way, it is possible to simulate all fault types and not only symmetrical faults. The results of the simulations are verified by some measurements and other simulations resulting from [23-24]. The HVDC point-to-point connection has been developed according to [25] and also takes into account positive and negative sequence control. The more detailed about studied system and grid code requirements discussed by authors in [6]. Figure 2 depicts the general diagram of the HIL test-bench that will be used during the tests.

Fig.2: Hardware-in-loop testing, laboratory test-bench and signals exchanged

Fig.3: Vendor distance protection performance for phase-to-ground fault with 40 MW generation level Protection zones and digital signals

3. Fault detection challenges in presence of PEC interfaced REGs power network

From the rigorous relay testing, it has been observed that the fault involving ground is not problematic for any of the vendor distance relays as depicted in Fig.3. Whereas, in case of ungrounded fault in presence of low power generation level (i.e. 40 MW) relays from all vendor do not trip as depicted in Fig.4(b). However, it perfectly works for same fault in presence of high power generation level (i.e. 200MW) as depicted in Fig.4(a). It can be seen that the impedance approaches gradually (during relay tripping) or abruptly (during relay failure) the first zone of the protection. The fact that in some cases the protection fails to operate implies that the relay fails to detect the fault.

Fig.4: Vendors distance relay performance for phase-to-phase fault with generation level (a) 200 MW Trip condition and, (b) 40 MW No-Trip Condition

Therefore, to overcome shortfall of existing distance relay FST-based hybrid fault detection algorithm has been developed. The computational complexity of FST is much lower than the S-transform. Therefore, the method is good choice for real-time applications for the time-frequency analysis of fault in presence of PEC interfaced REGs power network. The detailed analysis discussed in next section.

4. Proposed technique: Improvement of fault detection algorithm in existing distance element

A. Fast discrete S-Transforms(FDST)

This technique decreases the computational burden of the discrete S-transform by employing an intelligent decision mechanism by numerically filtering out the unwanted frequency information [26-31]. A frequency stack containing the significant frequencies using the FFT can be formed without

much computational burden. Only the frequencies present in the frequency stack are used for time localization computation, resulting in significant improvement in speed. With further help from a decision mechanism, the frequency values in the vicinity of the significant frequency components in the frequency stack are used for computation.

Consider that a time series $x(t)$ is sampled with a sampling period of T second to obtain N samples. The expression for discrete ST becomes

$$S\left(jT, \frac{n}{NT}\right) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x(kT) \cdot w\left((j-k)T, \frac{n}{NT}\right) \cdot e^{\left(-\frac{i2\pi kn}{N}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where

$f = n/NT$, $T =$ sampling interval, and the window function in the discrete domain is chosen as

$$w\left(jT, \frac{n}{NT}\right) = \frac{a+b\left|\frac{n}{NT}\right|^c}{r\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left((jT)^2 \left(a+b\left|\frac{n}{NT}\right|^c\right)^2 \div 2r^2\right) \quad (2)$$

where $j = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ represents a time point index, $n = 0, 1, \dots, (N/2)-1$ is a frequency point index of a given cycle, is the discrete time-domain signal, k is the time-domain shift required for the convolution with the window w , f and is the frequency point computed from the frequency point index of the signal. In (2), r and b are the scaling factors that control the number of oscillations in the window, a and c are positive constant. Setting the parameter c at some value between 0 to 1 contributes toward the capture of damped hidden frequencies. To obtain the FDST, the following computational steps using FFT are outlined:

Step1: *Appropriate choice of the frequency scaling is important for fast computation of the discrete S-transform algorithm. The choices in frequency scaling could be:*

Dyadic Scaling: *The dyadic scaling is defined as choosing frequency vector indices at the power of 2. So $k = \{2^0, 2^1, 2^2, \dots, 2^l\}$, $2^l < N$, where k is a frequency index. As opposed to $N/2$ number of time spectrum computations in the discrete S-Transform, the dyadic scale reduces it to $\log_2(N/2)$ and the logarithmic scale reduces it to $\log_e(N/2)$.*

Automatic Scaling: *In this scaling frequency sampling is performed such that only these dominant frequencies are included. The intermediate values in the scaling are approximated using different kinds of interpolation techniques. The choice of the interpolation technique is just a trade-off between required precision and the computational effort in interpolating.*

Step2: *Calculate the discrete Fourier Transform $X(k)$ of the signal samples $x(k)$ using FFT algorithm.*

Step3: *Set the width of the Band Pass Filter: This is chosen in accordance to uncertainty principle. Since frequency content falls within 3 to 4 kHz in most power signal disturbances, thus the raw signal is pre-processed through a band pass filter with cut-off frequency of nearly 4 kHz. M is the corresponding number of samples and $n(= M/2)$ is the index of the frequency samples.*

Step4: *The window function is recalculated from (2) with r being greater than 0 and “ n ” being decided using the scaling technique.*

Step5: *Shift the window function: The window function is then shifted and centred on the frequency band specified by the band pass filter for power system protection applications.*

Step6: *Multiply the FFT of input signal samples with the FFT of the window function as*

$$G(k, n) = X(k) * FFT(W(k, n))$$

Step7: *Calculate the inverse FFT as*

$$IFFT \text{ of } G(k, n) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} G(k, n) \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i k}{N}\right) \text{ And } S(k, n) = IFFT(G(k, n))$$

Step8: Further $S(k, n)$ is complex and it is represented as $S(k, n) = A(k, n) \exp(i\theta(k, n))$ where the quantity $A(k, n) = |S(k, n)|$ becomes the amplitude of the S-spectrum at a given frequency n , and $\theta(k, n) = \arctan(\text{Im}(S(k, n))/\text{Re}(S(k, n)))$ is the phase of the S-spectrum at the same frequency.

Step9: Derive spectral energy index of signal using time-frequency contour analysis step8.

A. Performance of FST based fault detection algorithm

It has been observed that none of the distance relays is able to detect ungrounded faults on the transmission line integrated with low DFIG level (i.e. below equal to 40 MW). Therefore, to improve the performance of fault detection element in existing distance relay, a FST-based hybrid algorithm has been used in this paper. The FST-based fault detection algorithm supervises the existing distance relay fault detection element. This algorithm is only activated (in absence of zero sequence component) during an ungrounded fault with low generation level. The other types of line fault cases are easily handled by existing distance protection algorithm. Therefore, during this condition, the FST-algorithm is in deactivated mode (in presence of zero sequence component) based on the fault detection logic criteria. The hybrid algorithm for improvement of distance relay fault detection element is depicted in Fig.5. The new fault detection index will be based on FST. The time-frequency contour analysis is used for fault analysis. The spectral energy index (SPE_{INDEX}) derived from FST used for detecting the fault condition. The proposed fault detection method able to detect fault within half cycle from the inception of fault, when a fault occurs in zone-1. Whenever, a fault occurs in zone-2 of the lines then the delay associated with zone-2 is added to the response time of the proposed method. The failed cases of studied distance relays has been tested with the proposed hybrid scheme and depicted in Fig.6 and Fig.7. The two failed cases are; (1) Case-1: Phase-to-phase fault with 40MW generation level and, (2) Case-2: Three-phase fault with 40MW generation level. Table-1 shows the results of the proposed algorithm in different operating conditions. Hence, the response time for fault detection is does not affected by varying the operating condition. The threshold SPE_{INDEX} , which is decided based on the influence of different uncertainties including load-change issue, will be definitely less for the FST approach compared to the other existing methods. This implies that the number of false detections will be quite less with this approach. The set threshold is also found immune to 20 dB noise.

Fig.5: FST based hybrid algorithm for improvement of distance relay fault detection element

Fig.6: FST-based algorithm performance for phase-to-phase fault with 40MW generation level

Fig.7: FST-based algorithm performance for three-phase fault with 40MW generation level

B. Fault detection algorithm real-time testing architecture

Many communication protocols have been well established in power system applications. Those communication protocols include DNP3.0 and IEC 61850 protocol series. The GTNET card is a communication interface card available in RTDS. The card was developed in order to accommodate widely utilized communication protocols in power systems during real time simulations. The external client is implemented using MATLAB M script. The necessary socket communication related commands were introduced in MATLAB version 2016b. The proposed algorithm has been tested on RTDS platform using GTNET-SKT (Socket) protocol. The SKT protocol is provided as a means to communicate with the RTDS using TCP or UDP sockets (GTNETx2 card). The SKT protocol represents both integer and floating-point numbers as 4-bytes in the packet. Floating-point numbers are single precision (32 bit) and are represented using IEEE754 format. The number of points and type of each point (integer or float) are defined in the SKT component in RSCAD/Draft. The maximum size for a packet corresponds to 300 data points (update rate 1000Hz) or 1200 bytes. The on-line real-time realization architecture of proposed method and performance assessment depicted in Fig.8-9.

Fig.8: (a) Overall architecture in real-time testing platform and, (b) GTNET-SKT block used for interfacing with PC

Fig.9: Performance assessments of proposed method and vendors relay during phase-phase fault with 40MW

Table 1: Testing performance

No of Test	Characteristics			Existing Method		Proposed Method	
	Faults Type	Fault Zone	Generation Level (MW)	Trip Decision	Trip Time (ms)	Trip Decision	Trip Time (ms)
1	LG	1	200	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
2	LG	1	40	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
3	LLG	1	200	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
4	LLG	1	40	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
5	LL	1	200	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
6	LL	1	40	No trip	-	Trip	<20
7	LLL	1	200	Trip	<45	Trip	<20
8	LLL	1	40	No trip	-	Trip	<20
9	LG	2	200	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
10	LG	2	40	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
11	LLG	2	200	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
12	LLG	2	40	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
13	LL	2	200	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
14	LL	2	40	No trip	-	Trip	<415
15	LLL	2	200	Trip	<440	Trip	<415
16	LLL	2	40	No trip	-	Trip	<415

C. Performance of FST for other types of fault

The all 4 different vendors distance protection fault detection element not able detect only phase-phase fault type with 40 MW generation level , as discussed in section-3. This is the common problem noticed in all 4 vendors product. Whereas, for other types of line fault some vendors product operate correctly and some vendors product miss operate some time. This happens mainly because of different fault detection algorithm used by each vendor in there product and vendors correct it by changing some setting of distance protection feature (used inside the product). Therefore, to make the proposed method cost effective its applied only for ungrounded fault with low generation level(40MW) in presence of PEC interfaced REGs power transmission network. Further, the proposed method also can be used as advanced fault detection and phase selection for future manufacturer relay product. Some, of the fault detection and phase selection results for conventional synchronous generator based power transmission network presented in appendix section of the paper.

5. Conclusions

An FST based hybrid algorithm to supervised existing distance relay fault detection element has been proposed in this paper. This method is successfully implemented to detect ungrounded fault in presence of low renewable generation level. The following are the specific observations to conclude:

- 1) The technique starts at pre-processing the current signal retrieved at the relaying point to derive the S-matrix. The S-contours are derived from the S-matrix, which are basically time–frequency contours that time-localizes the fault event. The spectral energy content of the S-contours is computed to register the faults.
- 2) Stockwell transform exhibit the ability of identifying the power system disturbance due to noise or transient. This cannot be achieved by existing methods because of their sensitivity to noise.
- 3) The FST based algorithm is needed to deal with ungrounded fault. The other fault cases can easily be handled by existing distance relay fault detection element.FST is low computational burden form of Stockwell transform , which is quiet suitable for on-line application.
- 4) The proposed method performs desirably during capacitor bank switching and increase or decrease of loading. The selection of the threshold is important for accurate detection which is decided by the influencing factors, such as noise and other uncertainties.

Various cases are successfully simulated and the test results are presented in the paper. As it was shown in the paper that the FST based hybrid algorithm is able to utilized to detect short circuit faults that cannot be detected by distance relays of different vendors. Validation on RTDS platform enhances the applicability of the proposed scheme in real-world scenario.

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7. Disclaimer

This paper reflects the MIGRATE consortium view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

8. References

- [1] U. Secretariat, "Kyoto protocol reference manual on accounting of emissions and assigned amounts," Kyoto Protocol Reference Manual, 2007.
- [2] A. Foley and A. G. Olabi, "Renewable energy technology developments, trends and policy implications that can underpin the drive for global climate change," 2017.
- [3] International Energy Agency, "Renewables 2017: Analysis and forecasts to 2022," October 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/renewables/>
- [4] IEEE 1547 std: with interconnecting resources with distributed power systems, IEEE, July 2003 (R2008).
- [5] ENTSOE: Implementation Guideline For Network Code - "Requirements for Grid Connection Applicable to all Generators", 2013 online available: <http://www.entsoe.eu>.
- [6] M. Popov, Rahul Dubey, J. Chavez, M. Villén, E. Martínez, S. Borroy, S. López, D. López, L. Pindado and, R. Andrino, "Exposing available distance relay operations near high wind penetration" OP31, PAC World Sofia, Bulgaria 2018.
- [7] M. Tsili, S. Papathanassiou, "A Review of Grid Code Technical Requirements for Windfarms", *IET Renewable Power Generation*, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp.308-332, 2009.
- [8] J. A. Jodice, "Relay Performance Testing: a Power System Relaying Committee publication," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 169-171, Jan 1997.
- [9] R. Dubey, S. R. Samantaray and B. K. Panigrahi, "Simultaneous impact of unified power flow controller and off-shore wind penetration on distance relay characteristics," in *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 1869-1880, 2014.
- [10] R. Dubey, S. R. Samantaray and B. K. Panigrahi, "Adaptive distance protection scheme for shunt-FACTS compensated line connecting wind farm," in *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 247-256, 2016.
- [11] S. De Rijcke, P.S. Perez, J. Driesen: "Impact of wind turbines equipped with doubly-fed induction generators on distance relaying", Power and Energy Society General Meeting, 2010 IEEE.
- [12] I. Xyngi, M. Popov: An Intelligent Algorithm for the Protection of Smart Power Systems, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids*, Vol. 4, No. 3, August 2013, pp. 1541-1548.
- [13] TU DELFT, CIRCE, The University of Manchester, Schneider Electric, REE, RTE, Elering, «MIGRATE PROJECT: Deliverable 4.1 Accurate models for desktop protection studies and HiL tests,» 2016.
- [14] A. Hooshyar, M.A. Azzouz, E. F. El-Saadany: Distance Protection of Lines Emanating From Full-Scale Converter-Interfaced Renewable Energy Power Plants-Part I: Problem Statement, *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, Vol. 30, No. 4, August 2015, pp. 1770-1780.
- [15] A. Hooshyar, M.A. Azzouz, E. F. El-Saadany: Distance Protection of Lines Emanating From Full-Scale Converter-Interfaced Renewable Energy Power Plants-Part II: Solution, *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, Vol. 30, No. 4, August 2015, pp. 1781-1791.
- [16] Tennet TSO GmbH, *Grid code –High and extra high voltage-*, Status first November 2015.
- [17] D. S. Chan and J. C. Phang, "Analytical Methods for the Extraction of Solar-Cell Single-and Double-Diode Model Parameters from I-V Characteristics," *IEEE Transactions on Electronic Devices*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 286-293, February 1987.
- [18] G. Farivar, B. Asaei, S. Mehrnami, "An Analytical Solution for Tracking Photovoltaic Module MPP," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol.3, no.3, July 2013.
- [19] M. Mirhosseini, J. Pou, B. Karanayil y V. G. Agelidis, Positive- and negative-sequence control of grid-connected photovoltaic systems under unbalanced voltage conditions, de *Power Engineering Conference (AUPEC), Australasian Universities*, Hobart, TAS, 2013.

- [20] H. Shariatpanah, R. Fadaeinedjad and M. Rashidinejad, "A New Model for PMSG-Based Wind Turbine With Yaw Control," in *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 929-937, Dec. 2013.
- [21] M. Chinchilla, S. Arnaltes, J.C. Burgos: Control of Permanent-Magnet Generators Applied to Variable-Speed Wind-Energy Systems Connected to the Grid, *IEEE TEC*, Vol. 21, No. 1 Mar. 2006, pp. 130-135.
- [22] R. Pena, C. J. Clare y G. M. Asher, Doubly fed induction generator using back-to-back PWM converters and its application to variable speed wind-energy generation, IEE, 1996.
- [23] L. Xu, et al: VSC Transmission operating under unbalanced AC conditions – Analysis and Control Design, *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, Vol. 20, No. 1, 2005, pp. 427-434.
- [24] H. Song, K. Nam: Dual Current Control Scheme for PWM Converter under Unbalanced Input Voltage Conditions, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, Vol. 46, No. 5, October 1999, pp. 953-959.
- [25] H. Chong, R. Li, J. Bumby: Unbalanced Grid Fault Ride Through Control for a Wind Turbine Inverter, *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, Vol. 44, No. 3, 2008, pp. 845-856.
- [26] R. G. Stockwell, L. Mansinha and R. P. Lowe, "Localization of the complex spectrum: the S transform," in *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 998-1001, Apr 1996.
- [27] P. K. Dash, B. K. Panigrahi and G. Panda, "Power quality analysis using S-transform," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 406-411, April 2003.
- [28] Brown, Robert; Lauzon, M. Louis; Frayne, Richard, "Signal processing with fast S-transforms" Patent No. 8458240 (available <https://patents.google.com/patent/US8458240>).
- [29] A. H. Osman and O. P. Malik, "Transmission line distance protection based on wavelet transform," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 515-523, Apr. 2004.
- [30] P. K. Dash, S. R. Samantaray, G. Panda, and B. K. Panigrahi, "Timefrequency transform approach for protection of parallel transmission lines," *Inst. Eng. Technol. Gen. Transm. Distrib.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 30-38, 2007.
- [31] C. R. Pinnegar and L. Mansinha, "Time local Fourier analysis with a scalable, phase modulated analyzing function: The S-transform with a complex window," *Signal Process.*, vol. 84, no. 7, pp. 1167-1176, 2004.